

Management

SUBSCRIBERS' PREFERENCE TOWARDS MOBILE COMMUNICATION SERVICE – AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Fulfilling the preference of the subscribers is an important task to every marketer. As it is a competitive world, the retaining the subscribers is difficult job to the service providers. Today, preference of the subscribers varies from one to one. Due to huge competition in the service sector, there are so many service providers available. Therefore each and every service provider has to focus on lots of aspects in connection with subscriber's preference. In that, the subscribers' preference must be identified and fulfilled by the service providers. Thus the service providers need to focus on fulfilling the subscribers' needs, wants and preference to maintain their position in the competitive market. As the success of the marker is depending upon the subscribers' preference, the marketer should know it and try to fulfill it. This study analyses the subscribers' preference towards mobile communication service in Tuticorin District.

Keywords:

Subscribers, Service, preference, Market, Communication & Mobile.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Customers' preference is nothing but likes and wants of the customers towards a particular product or service. Customer like the product based on so many aspects and reasons. If our product or service has some preferable aspects, then customer will retain with us. If not so, then they may switch over from our brand to another brand. Therefore, it is very important to know the preferences, likes, dislikes, wants and so on. Because the successes of the product is fully depending upon the satisfaction of the customers.

As customers are king of the market, fulfilling the preference of the subscribers is the indication of success and possibility for survival of the company in a market. Knowing the preference of the subscribers is a vital role to the marker. It is little difficulty that fulfilling all the subscribers

as per their preference needs and wants. Thus, subscribers' preference has become a significant research area in view of fulfilment the subscribers.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the factors determining the preference of the subscribers.
- To study the subscribers' preferable services.
- To identify the possible services to the subscribers.
- To offer suggestions to provide suitable service to fulfil the subscribers' preference.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

“The greatest challenge in marketing is fulfilling their customer's needs, wants and preference. Preference is the mental thoughts of the customers. It may vary from person to person and so on. If the preference of the customers is fulfilled then they have positive attitude towards the products or services, otherwise, it may be vice versa. Fulfilling the customers' needs, wants and preference is a toughest task to the manufactures or service providers. For that, the service providers first of all, must know the subscribers' preference and so on. Then only they can offer the service as per the subscribers' preference. Every subscriber possesses the right to prefer any products or service according to his or her view. Over the last decades, subscribers' preference is increasing for day by day. As there are a number of service providers and there is severe competition among these service providers, the service provider has to concentrate on the subscribers' preference individual wise. In this context the study has been undertaken, to find out the subscribers' preference towards mobile communication service providers in Tuticorin Dist.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is covered the subscribers' preference towards mobile communication service, who are in Tuticorin District. As Tuticorin District has more industry, agricultural lands, handcraft products and four ways of transport facilities, there are good numbers of mobile subscribers in both urban and rural areas, having advanced technology communication equipment. For the study, we have considered both the government and private service providers in this study area. Further, the study is confined to factors that influence the subscribers to prefer a particular service operator and the subscribers' attitudes towards various mobile service. As regards subscribers' preference towards mobile communication service, the study is confined to Subscribers' Preference on Mobile Communication Service in Tuticorin District.

5. PREFERENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

5.1.PREFERENCE TOWARDS LIFETIME SCHEME

The lifetime scheme is offered with the base of certain periods, according to the service providers. Generally, it is 10 years. After 10 years, the subscriber has to renew their account with a minimum recharge amount for continuing the service (SIM's Validity). Hence, it is important

to analyse the opinion of the subscribers regarding lifetime scheme. The following table shows the opinion regarding the lifetime scheme by the respondents

Table 1.1: Preference towards Lifetime Scheme by the Respondents

Preference	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
Highly hasn't preferred	1	1.0	46	7.4	47	6.5
Not preferred	13	12.5	46	7.4	59	8.1
Neutral	17	16.3	93	15.0	110	15.2
Preferred	29	27.9	227	36.5	256	35.3
Highly preferred	44	42.3	210	33.8	254	35.0

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that in the public sector, only one per cent of the respondents is highly not preferring lifetime scheme, 12.5 per cent of the respondents are not preferring lifetime scheme, 16.3 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 27.9 percent of the respondents are preferring life time scheme and 42.3 per cent of the respondents are highly preferred lifetime scheme.

In the private sector, 7.4 per cent of the respondents are highly not preferring lifetime scheme, 7.4 per cent of the respondents are not preferring lifetime scheme, 15 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 36.5 percent of the respondents prefer life time scheme and 33.8 per cent of the respondents are highly preferred lifetime scheme.

Totally, 6.5 per cent of the respondents are highly not preferring lifetime scheme, 8.1 per cent of the respondents are not preferring lifetime scheme, 15.2 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 35.3 percent of the respondents are preferring life time scheme and 35 per cent of the respondents are highly preferred lifetime scheme.

It is inferred that 35.3 per cent of the respondents prefer lifetime scheme.

5.2.PREFERENCE OF USING GPRS BY THE RESPONDENTS

GPRS means General Packet Radio System; it is a packet internet system. The subscribers can use it for downloading, browsing, getting information and chatting. For that minimum amount is charged by the service provider from the subscribers. The following table shows the preference of using GPRS by the respondents.

Table 1.2: Preference of Using GPRS

GPRS	Preference of Using GPRS	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
		(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
Downloading	Yes	18	17.3	162	26.0	180	24.8
	No	86	82.7	460	74.0	546	75.2
Information	Yes	31	29.8	87	14.0	118	16.3

	No	73	70.2	535	86.0	608	83.7
Purchase	Yes	14	13.5	64	10.3	78	10.7
	No	90	86.5	558	89.7	648	89.3
Chat	Yes	25	24.0	103	16.6	128	17.6
	No	79	76.0	519	83.4	598	82.4
Map	Yes	21	20.2	83	13.3	104	14.3
	No	83	79.8	539	86.7	622	85.7

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows the respondents' preference towards GPRS usage and is described below.

Downloading

In the public sector, 17.3 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for downloading, 82.7 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for downloading. In the private sector, 26 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for downloading, 74 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for downloading. Totally, 24.8 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for downloading. 75.2 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for downloading.

Information

In the public sector, 29.8 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for getting information and 70.2 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for getting information. In the private sector, 14 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for getting information and 86 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for getting information. Totally, 16.3 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for getting information and 83.7 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for getting information.

Chat

In the public sector, 24 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for chatting in various social networking sites whereas 76 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for chatting. In the private sector, 16.6 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for chatting in various social networking sites whereas 83.4 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for chatting. Totally, 17.6 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for chatting in various social networking sites whereas 82.4 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for chatting.

Purchase

In the public sector, 13.5 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for purchasing whereas 86.5 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for purchasing. In the private sector, 10.3 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for purchasing whereas 89.7 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for purchasing. Totally, 10.7 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for purchasing whereas 89.3 per cent of the respondents do not prefer GPRS for purchasing.

Map

In the public sector, 20.2 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for locating area/places through maps and the remaining 79.8 per cent of the respondents do not prefer map through GPRS. In the private sector, 13.3 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for locating area/places through maps and the remaining 86.7 per cent of the respondents do not prefer map

through GPRS. Totally, 14.3 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for locating area/places through maps and the remaining 85.7 per cent of the respondents do not prefer map through GPRS.

It is inferred that 24.8 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for downloading, 16.3 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for collecting information, 10.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to use GPRS for online purchasing, 17.6 percent of the respondents prefer GPRS for Chatting and 14.3 per cent of the respondents prefer map while on travel or before going to any place.

5.3.PREFERENCE OF FULL TALK TIME OFFER

The full talk time offers are provided by the service provider to the subscribers uniquely or for the entire subscribers. No service tax and access charges will be deducted for the full talk time offer. The entire amount recharged will be added as balance in the main account of the subscriber. For instance, recharging for Rs.10 means, the full value (Rs.10) will be credited to the account. It is one of the best strategies to attract the subscribers by the service providers. The full talk time offers are given from the lowest denomination to higher denomination. Hence, it is important to analyse the preference of full talk time offers by the respondents.

Table 1.3: Preference of Full Talk Time

Full Talk Time (Rs)	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
Upto 50	0	0	32	5.1	32	4.4
51-100	18	17.3	223	35.9	241	33.2
101 to 200	41	39.4	222	35.7	263	36.2
Above 200	45	43.3	145	23.3	190	26.2

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table describes that in the public sector, none of the respondent prefers to avail full talk time offer upto Rs.50, 17.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to avail full talk time offers from Rs.51 to 100, 39.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to recharge from Rs.101 to 200, 43.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to recharge full talk time offers above Rs. 200.

In the private sector, 5.1 per cent of the respondents prefer to avail full talk time offers upto Rs.50, 35.9 per cent of the respondents prefer to avail full talk time offers from Rs.51 to 100, 35.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to recharge full time offers from Rs.101 to 200, 23.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to recharge full talk time offers above Rs. 200.

In total, 4.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to avail full talk time offer upto Rs.50, 33.2 per cent of the respondents prefer to avail full talk time offers from Rs.51 to 100, 36.2 per cent of the respondents prefer to recharge full time offers from Rs.101 to 200, 26.2 per cent of the respondents prefer to recharge full talk time offers above Rs. 200.

It is found that 36.2 per cent of the respondents preferred full talk time offers from Rs.101 to Rs. 200.

5.4.PREFERRED TIME FOR MAKING CALLS BY THE RESPONDENTS

The time plays a vital role in all aspects of life. A man schedules the entire work based on time. There is no separate time for using mobile phones. It renders 24 hour service, but people prefer to use it on their preferable time. Thus, it is important to analyse and identify the preferred time for making calls by the respondents.

Table 1.4: Preferred Time for Making Calls

Time	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
12 a.m. to 6 a.m.	2	1.9	30	4.8	32	4.4
6 a.m. to 12 p.m.	16	15.4	52	8.4	68	9.4
12 p.m. to 6 p.m.	33	31.7	104	16.7	137	18.9
6 p.m. to 12 a.m.	26	25.0	251	40.4	277	38.2
Always	27	26.0	185	29.7	212	29.2

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that in the public sector, 1.9 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 12 a.m. to 6 a.m., 15.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 6 a.m. to 12 p.m., 31.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 12 p.m. to 6 p.m., 25 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 6 p.m. to 12 a.m. and 26 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak always without any specific time.

In the private sector, 4.8 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 12 a.m. to 6 a.m., 8.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 6 a.m. to 12 p.m., 16.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 12 p.m. to 6 p.m., 40.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 6 p.m. to 12 a.m. and 29.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak always without any specific time.

Totally, 4.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 12 a.m. to 6 a.m., 9.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 6 a.m. to 12 p.m., 18.9 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 12 p.m. to 6 p.m., 38.2 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak during 6 p.m. to 12 a.m. and 29.2 per cent of the respondents prefer to speak always without any specific time. It is inferred that 31.7 per cent of the respondents of public sector speak between 12 p.m. to 6 p.m. and 40.4 per cent of the respondents of private sector speak between 6 p.m. to 12 a.m. 38.2 per cent of the respondents of private sector speak between 6 p.m. to 12 a.m.

5.5.PREFERRED TIME FOR SENDING SMS BY THE RESPONDENTS

Nowadays, most of the people prefer to send SMS to others with whom they wish to contact. Especially, it is popular among young people. Hence, it is important to analyse the time preferred by the respondents for sending SMS. The following table describes the time preferred by the respondents for sending SMS.

Table 1.5: Preferred Time for Sending SMS

Time	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
Not user	68	65.4	148	23.8	216	29.8
12 a.m. to 6 a.m.	4	3.8	26	4.2	30	4.1
6 a.m. to 12 p.m.	1	1.0	52	8.4	53	7.3
12 p.m. to 6 p.m.	2	1.9	44	7.1	46	6.3
6 p.m. to 12 a.m.	25	24.0	210	33.8	235	32.4
Always	4	3.8	142	22.8	146	20.1

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table 1.5 describes that in the public sector, 3.8 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 12 a.m. to 6 a.m., only one per cent of the respondent prefers to send SMS during 6 a.m. to 12 p.m., 1.9 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 12 p.m. to 6 p.m., 24 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 6 p.m. to 12 a.m., 3.8 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS always and 65.4 per cent of the respondents do not prefer sending SMS.

In the private sector, 4.2 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 12 a.m. to 6 a.m., 8.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 6 a.m. to 12 p.m., 7.1 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 12 p.m. to 6 p.m., 33.8 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 6 p.m. to 12 a.m., 22.8 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS always and 23.8 per cent of the respondents do not prefer sending SMS.

Totally, 4.1 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 12 a.m. to 6 a.m., 7.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 6 a.m. to 12 p.m., 6.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 12 p.m. to 6 p.m., 32.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS during 6 p.m. to 12 a.m., 20.1 per cent of the respondents prefer to send SMS always and 29.8 per cent of the respondents do not prefer sending SMS.

It is inferred that the majority of the respondents prefers to send SMS between 6 p.m. to 12 a.m.

5.6.PREFER TO GET PROMOTIONAL OFFERS

The service providers inform about promotional offers through SMS or calls to the subscribers. Hence, it is important to analyse the preference of subscribers towards receiving mode of promotional offers. Therefore, the preference in getting promotional offers' information of the respondents is gathered and results obtained are given below.

Table 1.6: Prefer to get Promotional Offers

Promotional Offers	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
SMS	39	37.5	394	63.3	433	59.6
Call	14	13.5	61	9.8	75	10.3

Both	1	1.0	25	4.0	26	3.6
Don't want	50	48.1	142	22.8	192	26.4

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that in the public sector, 37.5 per cent of the respondents prefer SMS to get information about promotional offers, 13.5 percent of the respondents prefer calls to know about promotional offers, only one per cent of the respondent wants to get information about promotional offers through SMS and calls and 48.1 percent of the respondents do not prefer to get information about promotional offers from the service provider.

In the private sector, 63.3 per cent of the respondents prefer SMS to get information about promotional offers, 9.8 percent of the respondents prefer calls to know about promotional offers, four per cent of the respondents want to get information about promotional offers through SMS and calls and 22.8 percent of the respondents do not prefer to get information about promotional offers from the service provider.

Totally, 59.6 per cent of the respondents prefer SMS to get information about promotional offers, 10.3 percent of the respondents prefer calls to know about promotional offers, 3.6 per cent of the respondent wants to get information about promotional offers through SMS and calls and 26.4 percent of the respondents do not prefer to get information about promotional offers from the service provider.

It is inferred that 59.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to get information about promotional offers through SMS.

5.7.PREFERENCE OF NETWORK

In India, there are two latest networks preferred by the subscribers, i.e. 2G and 3G networks. 2G means Second Generation mobile communication in which the voice and words can be communicated whereas in 3G network is Third Generation mobile communication, the face to face contact is possible. The 3G network is an advanced network than 2G. Hence, it is important to analyse the type of networks preferred by the respondents in the study area. The following table shows the preference of network by the respondents.

Table 1.7: Preference of Network of the Respondents

Technology	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
2G	89	85.6	470	75.6	559	77.0
3G	15	14.4	152	24.4	167	23.0

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table 1.7 shows that in the public sector, 85.6 per cent of the respondents prefer 2G network and 14.4 per cent of the respondents prefer 3G network, whereas in the private sector, 75.6 per cent of the respondents prefer 2G network and the remaining 24.4 per cent of the respondents prefer 3G network. Totally, 77 per cent of the respondents prefer 2G network and 23 per cent of the respondents prefer 3G network.

It is inferred that 77 per cent of the respondents prefer 2G network.

5.8.PREFERENCE TOWARDS CURRENT SERVICE PROVIDER

There are so many service providers offering mobile communication service. Out of them, respondents have selected their current service provider based on some reasons. Normally, mobile subscriber prefers the service providers based on the following reasons, i.e. tariff, offers, network, Value Added Services, facilities and internet speed. The following table describes the preference towards current service provider.

Table 1.8: Preference towards Current Service Provider by the Respondents

Preference	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
Tariff	16	15.4	87	14.0	103	14.2
Offers	3	2.9	89	14.3	92	12.7
Network	18	17.3	254	40.8	272	37.5
Value Added Services	31	29.8	15	2.4	46	6.3
Facilities	7	6.7	114	18.3	121	16.7
Internet speed	29	27.9	63	10.1	92	12.7

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that in public sector, 15.4 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to tariff, 2.9 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to offers offered by the service provider, 17.3 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider because of network coverage, 29.8 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to Value Added Services, 6.7 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to various facilities offered by the service provider, 27.9 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to speed of the internet services.

In private sector 14.0 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to tariff, 14.3 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to offers offered by the service provider, 40.8 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider because of proper network coverage, 2.4 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to Value Added Services, 18.3 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to various facilities offered by the service provider, 10.1 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to speed of the internet services.

Totally, 14.2 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to tariff, 12.7 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to offers offered by the service provider, 37.5 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider because of proper network coverage, 6.3 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to Value Added Services, 16.7 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to various facilities offered by the service provider, 12.7 per cent of the respondents prefer the current service provider due to speed of the internet services.

It is inferred that 37.5 per cent of the respondents prefer their sector for network coverage.

5.9. PREFERENCE OF PREPAID SERVICE PLAN

The researcher has focused on the prepaid plan preferred by subscribers. Here, the researcher analyses the subscriber's preference in selecting prepaid service plan. The following table shows the preference of prepaid service plan by the respondents.

Table 1.9: Preference of Prepaid Service Plan by the Respondents

Preference	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
Complete control over cost	61	58.7	216	34.7	277	38.2
Avoid monthly bill problem	40	38.5	268	43.1	308	42.4
Convenient activation & Deactivation	3	2.9	138	22.2	141	19.4

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table describes that in the public sector, 58.7 per cent of the respondents prefer prepaid plan due to complete control over cost, 38.5 per cent of the respondents prefer a prepaid plan for avoiding monthly bill problem and 2.9 per cent of the respondents prefer prepaid scheme for the purpose of convenient activation and deactivation of services.

In the private sector, 34.7 per cent of the respondents prefer prepaid plan due to complete control over cost, 43.1 per cent of the respondents prefer a prepaid plan for avoiding monthly bill problem and 22.2 per cent of the respondents prefer prepaid scheme for the purpose of convenient activation and deactivation of services.

Totally, 38.2 per cent of the respondents prefer prepaid plan due to complete control over cost, 42.4 per cent of the respondents prefer a prepaid plan for avoiding monthly bill problem and 19.4 per cent of the respondents prefer prepaid scheme for the purpose of convenient activation and deactivation of services.

It is inferred that 42.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to use prepaid service plan to avoid monthly bill problems.

5.10. PREFERENCE TOWARDS SMS BOOSTER

The SMS booster is a scheme, in which SMS can be sent at free of cost. Generally, students and youths prefer it. It is one of the value added services. The following table shows the preference towards the SMS booster by the respondents.

Table 1.10: Preference towards SMS Booster by the Respondents

Preference	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)

Yes	26	25.0	322	51.8	348	47.9
No	78	75.0	300	48.2	378	52.1

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that in the public sector, 25 per cent of the respondents prefer to use SMS booster and the remaining 75 per cent of the respondents do not prefer SMS booster. In the private sector, 51.8 per cent of the respondents prefer to use SMS booster and the remaining 48.2 per cent of the respondents do not prefer SMS booster. Totally, 47.9 per cent of the respondents prefer to use SMS booster and the remaining 52.1 per cent of the respondents do not prefer SMS booster.

It is inferred that 52.1 per cent of the respondents are not using SMS booster packs.

5.11. PREFERENCE TOWARDS RATE CUTTER

The rate cutter is a scheme used to reduce the subscriber's call cost. It is for 30 days or 90 days or 180 days. If the subscriber activates the rate cutter, then the subscriber can speak at low cost during that period of validity. Hence, it is important to analyze the preference towards rate cuts by the respondents.

Table 1.11: Preference towards Rate Cutter

Preference	Public sector		Private sector		Total	
	(n=104)	(100%)	(n=622)	(100%)	(n=726)	(100%)
Yes	73	70.2	452	72.7	525	72.3
No	31	29.8	170	27.3	201	27.7

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table 1.11 shows that in the public sector, 70.2 per cent of the respondents prefer to use rate cutter and the remaining 29.8 per cent of the respondents do not prefer rate cutter. In the private sector, 72.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to use rate cutter and the remaining 27.3 per cent of the respondents do not prefer rate cutter. Totally, 72.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to use rate cutter and the remaining 27.7 per cent of the respondents do not prefer rate cutter.

It is inferred that 72.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to use rate cutter.

6. FINDINGS

- It is inferred that 35.3 per cent of the respondents prefer lifetime scheme.
- It is inferred that 24.8 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for downloading, 16.3 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for collecting information, 10.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to use GPRS for online purchasing, 17.6 per cent of the respondents prefer GPRS for Chatting and 14.3 per cent of the respondents prefer map while on travel or before going to any place.
- It is found that 36.2 per cent of the respondents preferred full talk time offers from Rs.101 to Rs. 200.

- It is inferred that 31.7 per cent of the respondents of public sector speak between 12 p.m. to 6 p.m. and 40.4 per cent of the respondents of private sector speak between 6 p.m. to 12 a.m. 38.2 per cent of the respondents of private sector speak between 6 p.m. to 12 a.m.
- It is inferred that the majority of the respondents prefers to send SMS between 6 p.m. to 12 a.m.
- It is inferred that 59.7 per cent of the respondents prefer to get information about promotional offers through SMS.
- It is inferred that 37.5 per cent of the respondents prefer their sector for network coverage.
- It is inferred that 77 per cent of the respondents prefer 2G network.
- It is inferred that 42.4 per cent of the respondents prefer to use prepaid service plan to avoid monthly bill problems.
- It is inferred that 52.1 per cent of the respondents are not using SMS booster packs.
- It is inferred that 72.3 per cent of the respondents prefer to use rate cutter.

7. SUGGESTIONS

- It is better to offer more life time schemes.
- It has to be offered that full time offer from Rs101 to 200.
- Offers should be time based to avoid the signal and engage problem in the peak hours.
- The promotional offers can be sent through SMS to avoid the subscriber's disturbance.
- It is better that by implementing more towers to expand the network coverage.
- The service provider have to create more awareness about 3G and make the customer to use it.
- If the sms booster is low cost, then many people will use it.
- The rate cutter can be given at reasonable rate.

8. CONCLUSION

These days communication is unavoidable one in this modern society. It can be said that without communication nothing will happen. Such a vital role is played by communication in this information era. Due to development of science, nowadays, lots of communication modes are possible. Lots of social networks are providing the communication service at free of cost. Therefore it is significant duty of the service providers to know the preference of the subscribers and fulfill it. If so, the mobile communication will be in the communication world. Otherwise, mobile communication may be out of order like telegraph, traditional communication method where using birds& animals and so on.

9. REFERENCE

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